

Impact of clinical pharmacist-led interventions on glycemic control and quality of life among Iraqi patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus

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Abstract

Adequate glycemic management reduces complications related to diabetes and enhances the patient's quality of life. This study intended to evaluate pharmacist-led educational initiatives on glycemic management and quality of life (QOL) in individuals with type 1 diabetes. Pharmacists have a significant effect on the treatment of people with diabetes mellitus (DM) and a vital role in the enhancement of QOL. The objective of the study is to assess the efficacy of pharmacist-led intervention (PI) on the glycemic control and QOL of adult patients with type 1 DM in Iraq. The current study is a prospective, comparative, pre-post intervention study on patients with type 1 DM who attended a Specialized Center for Endocrinology and Diabetes in Baghdad, Al-Russafa. At baseline, the glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) and fasting blood glucose (FBS) were recorded, and the QOL was assessed by filling out the Quality-of-Life Scale for Iraqi Diabetes Mellitus Patients (QOLSID) questionnaire for each patient in both cohorts. After that, the patients in the interventional group received a face-to-face educational session, which lasted about 20–30 minutes. Then, an Arabic educational booklet was handed out to each patient in the interventional group. Three months later, the same parameters were re-measured for the same patients in both study groups. The percentage of patients demonstrating glycemic control was significantly higher than that of the control group (36.4% vs. 2.3%). The QOL score significantly increased in the intervention group (10.0% vs. 3.0%) compared to the control group. Our study concludes that a clinical pharmacist-led educational intervention may improve the glycemic control and QOL of type 1 DM.

Keywords

pharmacist-led educational intervention, diabetes, HbA1c, QOLSID, glycemic control

Introduction

DM is a metabolic illness. Approximately 2.0 million individuals in Iraq, aged between 20 and 79 years, are diagnosed with DM. In Iraq, it is 10.7%. In 2021, approximately 33.2 million individuals aged 20 to 79 across the 22 Arab nations received a diagnosis of diabetes

(Abusaib et al. 2020). It is characterized by full or partial insulin deficiency (Mikhael et al. 2018; Shehab et al. 2024). The incidence of DM type 1 boosts with age up to 14 years, but the DM can ensue at any age. Globally, DM type 1 began to improve in the 1950s, with an annual elevation of 3–4% within the past three decades (Norris et al. 2020).

DM type 1 is caused by an autoimmune attack on pancreatic β -cells, resulting in insulin deficiency. It involves genetic predisposition and environmental triggers such as viral infections (enteroviruses), dietary exposures, or other unknown stimuli. Autoantibodies appear in the pre-clinical phase and predict disease onset (Du et al. 2025).

Complications of DM type 1 diabetic ketoacidosis are life-threatening, and often, the initial presentation of DM type 1 Persistent hyperglycemia can lead to microvascular complications such as retinopathy, renal failure, and neuropathy and macrovascular complications such as cardiovascular disease that diminish health-related functioning, decrease QOL, and lower total life expectancy. Intensive glucose control significantly lessens the risk of these intricacies (Longendyke et al. 2024).

Management includes lifelong insulin therapy through multiple daily injections or insulin pumps. Glucose monitoring is essential, either by self-monitoring blood glucose or Education in nutrition, insulin adjustment, and self-care is critical. Newer therapies like teplizumab are being explored to delay disease progression in high-risk individuals (Janež et al. 2020; Herold et al. 2023).

Effective glycemic management may significantly diminish complications associated with diabetes and enhance QOL (Mikhael et al. 2019; Raheem et al. 2022). Uncontrolled hyperglycemia is the primary contributor to diabetes mellitus morbidity and death by inducing macrovascular and microvascular consequences (Guan et al. 2024). It may also adversely affect patients' physical and psychological well-being, so diminishing their quality of life (QOL), due to associated physical disabilities and mental health issues (Jammal 2023; Albai et al. 2024).

Glycated hemoglobin, representing the whole glycemic history of the previous 60 to 90 days, is a crucial indicator of long-term glycemic control. The risk of long-term effects from diabetes is strongly correlated with HbA1c, an objective indicator of persistent hyperglycemia. (Sherwani et al. 2016). QOL is a complex collection of objective and subjective dimensions, assessed through the experiencer's viewpoint and presumably mediated by cognitive factors (Megari 2013). Type 1 DM has no cure, and its management extends beyond pharmacological treatment (Hill et al. 2013). Lack of awareness and misconceptions about diabetes pose significant challenges to effective diabetes control. Therefore, knowledge and awareness of DM, self-management, and self-care practices are essential elements that can significantly influence patients' QOL (Ferreira et al. 2024).

Pharmacists' responsibilities extend beyond conventional filling and dispensing functions. Pharmacists play a crucial role in diabetes treatment and are among the most accessible healthcare specialists in primary care (Hussain and Bowen 2024). Numerous studies in Iraq have shown that pharmacist engagement and intervention via auditing, teaching, and interprofessional cooperation across diverse medical problems were beneficial and significant (Abbood et al. 2019; Jabri et al. 2020; Al-Musawi and Answer 2021; Abbas and Al-Metwali 2023; Ali and Al-Jumaili

2023; Falah and Jasim 2023; Khazal and Jamal 2023; Alkashaf and Mohammed 2024). Individual Planned Teaching (IPT) is an efficient educational strategy that enhances diabetes patients' understanding and proficiency in self-administering insulin (Al-Banna and Khuder 2015). Glycemic management can mainly be attained by pharmacological intervention; simultaneously, adherence to the pharmacological regimen is essential to achieving optimal therapeutic benefits (Cando et al. 2024).

No prior research has been conducted in Iraq to assess the effectiveness of pharmacist-led educational interventions on glycemic management and QOL. Enhancing patients' understanding of disease management, the function of insulin and its proper administration method, strategies for addressing hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia, and dietary and exercise considerations is crucial. This research aims to assess the effect of pharmacist-led educational programs on glycemic management and QOL of patients with DM type 1 in Iraq.

Materials and methods

Study design

The current study was a prospective, comparative, pre-post, interventional, randomized clinical study conducted in Iraq at the Specialized Center for Endocrinology and Diabetes in Iraq-Baghdad/Al-Russafa from 01 February 2024 to 31 July 2024.

Study population

The study recruited an appropriate sample of patients with type 1 DM by the specialists at the center.

Inclusion criteria

This research included patients with type 1 DM aged 18 years and older who could communicate and read Arabic for at least six months before demonstrating uncontrolled hyperglycemia (glycosylated hemoglobin HbA1C \geq 7% and/or FBS $>$ 130 mg/dl). Patients have been on the same regimen for the last three months, and we are accepting patients to participate in the research.

Exclusion criteria

Patients have been excluded from the research if they possess hearing, speech, or cognitive impairments that might hinder their acquisition of the queries and the educational material. Patients who have co-morbid illnesses that may compromise the study, including asthma, thyroid problems, adrenal gland disorders, celiac disease, or substantial renal impairment. Individuals administering corticosteroids. Patients necessitate alterations to their insulin regimen, namely an increase above 20% of the prior dosage (Kovil et al. 2017). Patients with diseases influencing red blood cell turnover,

including hemolytic and other anemias, G-6-PD deficiency, recent blood transfusions, administration of erythropoiesis-stimulating medications, end-stage renal illness, and pregnancy. Patients refuse to participate.

Study groups

Group 1: The interventional (active) group involved 44 type 1 diabetic patients who met the inclusion criteria and received an educational intervention about the disease, symptoms, and treatment designed and delivered by the researchers.

Group 2: The placebo comparator group (control) involved 43 type 1 diabetic patients who met the inclusion criteria and received ordinary care from their healthcare providers.

Study process: Firstly, we recorded the baseline of HbA1C and FBS for each patient in both groups (interventional and control); then, the researcher independently completed the structured questionnaire of QOLSID for each patient in both cohorts. After that, the patients in the interventional group received educational counseling. We prepared a reference Arabic booklet containing details about DM and its manifestations. Details about the insulin the patient uses (function, method of administration, side effects, and strategies for mitigation or prevention). Instructions for measuring blood glucose levels and using a glucometer, information on hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia management, dietary guidance, exercise education, and foot care education. An instructional leaflet was given to every patient who took part. In-person and telephone instruction sessions are part of comprehensive pharmacological counseling. The researcher used a mobile phone to stay in touch with the patients.

Educational sessions: Each patient in the interventional group received educational sessions lasting approximately 25–30 minutes. The patients were allowed to contact the clinical pharmacists throughout all the periods. Three months later, the same parameters will be remeasured for both interventional active and control groups to assess the degree of enhancement in glycemic control and QOL.

The educational session included details on diabetes and its manifestations and details on the insulin the patient uses (function, method of administration, side effects, and strategies for mitigation or prevention).

The study follows instructions for measuring blood glucose levels and using a glucometer, as well as information on hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia management, dietary guidance, exercise education, and foot care education. Every participating patient was provided with an informative booklet enclosing the aforementioned information. The instructional material applied the Dubai Health Authority's educational program for type 1 DM and self-management education and support program for

Figure 1. The study flowchart.

Iraqi patients with DM type 2 (Mikhael et al. 2020a). The flowchart displayed the study in Fig. 1.

Data collection and study instruments

The diabetes-specific quality of life scale covers overall health, social, psychological, and satisfaction aspects. The Iraqi DM patients' quality-of-life scale (QOLSID) consists of ten items. The first four questions and question ten directly examine satisfaction, question five social problems, questions six and seven emotion and stress, and questions eight and nine health issues. Questions have scores from 0 (poor) to 5 (best). Items 1–6 and 7 are reverse-scored. The direct sum of all item scores equals the total score. Good quality of life is indicated by scores > 32.5 (Mikhael et al. 2020b).

Statistical analysis

The Anderson-Darling test was employed to assess the adherence of continuous variables to normality; variables that adhered to the normal distribution were revealed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while those that did not adhere to the normal distribution were revealed as median (50th percentile) and interquartile range (25th to 75th percentile). A chi-square (X²) was employed to compare the proportion of categorical variables; an independent t-test was used to compare treatment and intervention (if data is not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney U test was employed), while a paired t-test was employed to compare the difference between baseline and end of therapy in each group (if data is not normally distributed, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was employed). Linear regression analysis assessed the relationship between various parameters, and the significance was assessed at $p = 0.05$.

Results

As illustrated in Table 1, there was no significant dissimilarity in mean age (28.56 ± 8.31 vs. 25.57 ± 7.99 years), sex (with a higher female-to-male ratio, 74.4/25.6% vs. 63.6/36.4%), marital status (married: 55.8% vs. 43.2%), education levels, median duration of DM (12 vs. 9 years), positive family history (18.6% vs. 9.1%), and number of injections between both groups.

Table 1. Assessment of demographic characteristics.

Variable	Intervention	Control	p-value
Number	44	43	-
Age (year), mean \pm SD	25.57 ± 7.99	28.56 ± 8.31	0.091 [#]
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	23.76 ± 3.78	26.57 ± 3.97	0.001 [#]
Sex, n (%)			0.277 [‡]
Female	28 (63.6%)	32 (74.4%)	
Male	16 (36.4%)	11 (25.6%)	
Marital status, n (%)			0.239 [‡]
Single	25 (56.8%)	19 (44.2%)	
Married	19 (43.2%)	24 (55.8%)	
Education level, n (%)			0.936 [‡]
Primary	15 (34.1%)	16 (37.2%)	
Secondary	19 (43.2%)	17 (39.5%)	
College	10 (22.7%)	10 (23.3%)	
Duration of DM, median (IQR)	9 (5.25–15.75)	12 (9–18)	0.069 [*]
Family history, n (%)	4 (9.1%)	8 (18.6%)	0.198 [‡]
Number of injections, n (%)			0.218 [‡]
Two	20 (45.5%)	14 (32.6%)	
Three	24 (54.5%)	29 (67.4%)	

[#]Independent t-test, [‡]chi-square test, ^{*}Mann-Whitney U test, IQR: interquartile range, BMI: body mass index, N: number.

The current study defined reasonable glycemic control as HbA1c below 7% (Elsayed et al. 2023). At baseline, there was no significant dissimilarity in HbA1c levels between the intervention and control groups ($9.15 \pm 1.56\%$ vs. $9.48 \pm 1.46\%$, $p = 0.317$). After three months, the intervention group experienced a 13.6% decline in HbA1c levels, nearly double the reduction observed in the control group (6.3%). The mean difference in HbA1c reduction between the two groups was

1.13% ($p < 0.001$), attributing a statistically significant effect to the pharmacist-led intervention.

Both groups exhibited reductions in fasting blood sugar (FBS) over time. The intervention group decreased from 186.3 ± 72.5 mg/dL to 167.7 ± 49.96 mg/dL, whereas the control group decreased from 225.3 ± 95.24 mg/dL to 182.7 ± 56.85 mg/dL, as illustrated in Table 2, Figs 2, 3.

Table 2. Assessment of glycemic control.

Variable	Intervention	Control	p-value
Number	44	43	
HbA1c (%), mean \pm SD			
Baseline	9.15 ± 1.56	9.48 ± 1.46	0.317 [#]
Three months	7.94 ± 1.45	9.07 ± 1.30	< 0.001 [#]
p-value	< 0.001 [†]	< 0.001 [†]	
Change, median (IQR)	-13.6 (-17.4 to -9.6)	-6.3 (-7.8 to 1.98)	< 0.001 [*]
Glycemic control after three months, n (%)			
Poor control	28 (63.6%)	42 (97.7%)	< 0.001 [‡]
Good control	16 (36.4%)	1 (2.3%)	
FBS (mg/dL), mean \pm SD			
Baseline	186.3 ± 72.5	225.3 ± 95.24	0.034 [#]
Three months	167.7 ± 49.96	182.7 ± 56.85	0.1926 [#]
p-value	0.230 [†]	0.001 [†]	
Change, median (IQR)	-2.9 (-28.7 to 21.5)	-16.7 (-32.9 to 3.1)	0.139 [*]

[#]Independent t-test, [‡]chi-square test, ^{*}Mann-Whitney U test, [†]paired t-test. IQR: interquartile range, FBS: fasting blood sugar, N: number.

The percentage of patients achieving reasonable glycemic control (HbA1c $< 7\%$) was 36.4% in the intervention group compared to only 2.3% in the control group ($p < 0.001$), demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention as illustrated in Table 2.

Regarding QOL, the intervention group exhibited a significant improvement, with median QOL scores increasing from 28.5 (IQR: 24–32) at baseline to 33 (IQR: 29.25–35) at three months ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, the control group exhibited a minor elevation from 26 (IQR: 22–31) to 26 (IQR: 24–31) ($p = 0.031$). The median percentage elevation in QOL scores was 10.0% (IQR: 6.15–20.6) in the intervention group versus 3.0% (IQR: 0.0–11.1) in the control group ($p < 0.001$), as demonstrated in Table 3, Fig. 4.

Figure 2. Assessment of change in HbA1c. **A.** Absolute HbA1c value; **B.** change in HbA1c from baseline. *** means the significance at $p < 0.001$, while **** means the significance at $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 3. Assessment of FBS change. **A.** Absolute FBS value; **B.** change in FBS value from baseline. ** means the significance at $p < 0.01$.

Figure 4. Violin plot of QoL score. **A.** QoL score at baseline; **B.** QoL score at the end of the study; **C.** change in QoL from baseline. *** means the significance at $p < 0.001$ and **** means the significance at $p < 0.0001$.

Table 3. Assessment of quality-of-life score.

Variable	Intervention	Control	p-value [†]
Number	44	43	-
QoL score (%), median (IQR)			
Baseline	28.5 (24–32)	26 (22–31)	0.200
Three months	33 (29.25–35)	26 (24–31)	< 0.001
p-value	< 0.001 [†]	0.031 [†]	
% Change, median (IQR)	10.0 (6.15–20.6)	3.0 (0.0–11.1)	< 0.001

[†] Wilcoxon signed-rank test, IQR: interquartile range, N: number.

Discussion

This research revealed that pharmacists' active participation in delivering diabetes educational initiatives, supplemented by printed resources for home use, could enhance patients' understanding of DM and its drugs, adherence to treatment, and glycemic control in type 1 DM outpatient care in Iraq. The attendees improved knowledge and adherence and targeted FBS after the instructional program compared to prior assessments.

Previous studies observed comparable outcomes, indicating that a 6-month pharmacist-led teaching program led to a mean decrease of 1.19% in HbA1c levels among individuals in the intervention group, where the results align with the results of earlier published studies (Krass et

al. 2007; Jahangard-Rafsanjani et al. 2015; Butt et al. 2016). Higher decreases in HbA1c levels have been revealed when pharmacist-led therapies have been employed for more than six months (Chua et al. 2014). Effective glycemic management may decrease the likelihood of complications associated with DM. People exhibiting inadequate glycemic control (HbA1c > 7%) are often at elevated risk for DM-related conditions; a 1% drop in HbA1c levels correlates with a 25 percent decline in the incidence of these conditions (Chen et al. 2023; Tan et al. 2023). In the current research, the enhancement in the mean of FBS seen throughout the study interval was only marginally evident. This conclusion contradicts the prior research, which showed a significant decrease in the mean FBS levels of individuals with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus following a 90-day follow-up intervention in centers (Farsaei et al. 2011). Our findings align with previously published results that demonstrated glycemic control was attained in 19.2% of patients for fasting plasma glucose levels and 23.1% for postprandial blood glucose measurements (Suprapti et al. 2022). In the Iranian research, no significant dissimilarity was revealed between the groups at the end of the 5 months; however, the decrease in HbA1c levels was elevated in the intervention group after the pharmacist's intervention, which included both a pamphlet and

a phone call. For type 2 diabetes mellitus, this outcome may be attributable to the short follow-up duration, diverse patient demographics, or cultural influences (Jahangard-Rafsanjani et al. 2015).

This finding demonstrates a significant difference in the mean values and the mean change of QoL scores between the intervention and control groups at the end of the research. This outcome is comparable to the results of previous research, which indicated a significant difference comparing the mean QoL throughout the baseline to the study completion within the interventional population (Sriram et al. 2011; Adibe et al. 2013). The results indicate that the educational sessions offered to the participants directly influenced their overall quality of life. A Jordanian study revealed that patients with DM type 2 who received pharmacist-led intervention, including a phone call and instructional booklet, in an outpatient diabetes clinic had enhanced self-reported medication adherence after six months, in contrast to minimal improvement in the standard care group; they also reported a decline in A1c of 0.8% over six months. In contrast, the usual care group exhibited a mean elevation of 0.1% in HbA1C compared to baseline (Jarab et al. 2012).

Differences in income, education, and access to healthcare can affect health outcomes, lifestyle choices, and entrance to resources. People from lower socioeconomic surroundings may have restricted access to quality healthcare, healthy food, or healthy education. Furthermore, individuals with limited healthcare access may delay seeking medical attention. All of these factors and more may influence individuals' health outcomes. However, the research had limitations to consider when considering the findings.

Presently, limited educational programs are available in DM clinics in Iraq for individuals with diabetes; however, our research introduced a new strategy by teaching patients numerous aspects of diabetes-related self-care alongside illness information through pharmacists.

Conclusion

A pharmacist-led educational program conducted on Iraqi patients in Iraq enhances their understanding of diabetes and related medications, adherence to treatment, and glycemic control. This research advocates for integrating clinical pharmacists into multidisciplinary healthcare teams within hospital and outpatient settings and for adopting such interventions into diabetes management programs to achieve optimal patient outcomes. The research emphasizes that pharmacist-led educational programs, adopted by teaching Iraqi patients several characteristics of diabetic-related self-care alongside illness knowledge, showed a significant difference in the mean values and the change in QOL scores between the intervention and control groups at the study end. Our outcome is comparable to the results

of previous research, which indicated a significant dissimilarity in the mean QOL throughout the baseline. The results indicate that the educational sessions presented to the Iraqi participants had an immediate and positive impact on their overall quality of life. Furthermore, our study demonstrates a groundbreaking investigation of the effects of pharmacist-led educational programs in Iraq, making a compelling case for their widespread adoption in the fight against diabetes.

Limitations of the study

The study's primary drawbacks were its single-center design and small sample size, which might have limited how broadly the results could be employed. A short follow-up period can make it more difficult to assess how long the results have improved. Recall bias may have occurred because a significant portion of the patient data was obtained through questionnaires administered during in-person interviews.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Ethical committee approval

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Data type: jpeg

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